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New locality of *Pamphilius ignymontiensis* Lacourt, 1973 in Poland (Hymenoptera, Symphyta, Pamphiliidae)¹

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a new locality of a very rare representative of the Pamphiliidae family, namely the *Pamphilius ignymontiensis* Lacourt. Four specimens of this species were caught in the centre of the country, in Kampinos National Park.

Key words: Hymenoptera, Symphyta, Pamphiliidae, *Pamphilius ignymontiensis*, new locality, Poland

1. INTRODUCTION

Pamphilius ignymontiensis Lacourt was described relatively recently, in 1973. Along with the previously known species: *P. aurantiacus* (Giraud) and *P. lethierryi* (Konow) it forms a set of European species inhabiting maple trees (*Acer* spp.). *P. alternans* (Costa) should probably also be included in that group.

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Although the host plant of this latter species is still unknown, the morphology of adults is very similar to that of the former ones. This particularly concerns male copulating organs, whose penis valves are very similar between the above mentioned species, and at the same time are considerably different from other species, thus forming a separate, maple-related group.

Out of the 4 species mentioned above only two have been reported from our country so far, namely *P. ignymontiensis* and *P. aurantiacus* (Huflejt 1997).

The remaining two: *P. lethierryi* and *P. alternans* are known from neighbouring countries, such as Germany, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Ukraine and although they have not been found in our country yet, they are very likely to occur in Poland. Below we present new information about *P. ignymontiensis* occurrence in our country.

2. MATERIALS

Insects were caught from April to July 2020 with Moericke traps, whose content was replaced every two weeks. The collected material was sorted into taxa and then passed to specialists to study.

3. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

In the latter half of April one male was caught (Figs 2-3), and in the first half of May - 3 females (Fig. 1) of *P. ignymontiensis*.

The new locality is as follows:

- Kampinos National Park, Bieliny, UTM: DC59, 15-30 IV 2020, 1 ♂, 1-15 V 2020, 3 ♀ ♀, Moericke trap, leg. D. Marczak.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Figs 1-2. Adults of *Pamphilius ignymontiensis* Lacourt, collected in Kampinos National Park in 2020, dorsal view. **1** - female; **2** - male.

Fig. 3. *Pamphilius ignymontiensis* Lacourt – a left penis valve of male aedeagus (outer view).

All the specimens are in the former author's (JB) collection, at the Department of Forest Protection of Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW), in Rogów.

P. ignymontiensis was first and only once reported from Poland by Huflejt (1997). The author recorded 4 males from four localities (Fig. 4), out of which two are within the capital city of Warsaw. The locality in Kampinos National Park is thus the fifth place to find *P. ignymontiensis* (Table 1).

The species was caught in the area of the former Bieliny village. That now comprises mid-forest clearings, with single maple, elm and oak trees (Figs 5-6). The spots with traps are well sunlit, and due to the surrounding forest air temperature is high, while air circulation is poor, creating xerothermic climate on the clearing.

The traps were hung on a Norway maple of diameter at breast height at 20-30 cm, about 1.8 m above the ground. There are no other maple species in the vicinity, so it can be assumed that the *P. ignymontiensis* develops on Norway maples (*Acer platanoides* L.) in the described locality. This species of maple is given as a host plant for *P. ignymontiensis* by Lacourt (1973), Viitasaari (1987), Shinohara & Blank (2003) and Roller & Macek (2017). Lacourt (1995), Viitasaari (op. cit.), Roller & Macek (op. cit.), Achterberg & Aartsen (1986) and Haris (2020) also claim the field maple (*Acer campestre* L.) is its host plant.

The other species, *P. aurantiacus*, is connected with the sycamore and is probably more likely to be found in submontane and montane areas than Polish lowlands. The only locality of *P. aurantiacus* in Poland found so far is situated in the Świętokrzyskie Mts. (Huflejt 1997).

Fig. 4. Known localities of *Pamphilius ignymontiensis* Lacourt in Poland.

Table 1. Description of the locality where *Pamphilius ignymontiensis* Lacourt was found in 2020.

No	Locality name	GPS coordinates UTM grid	Short description
1	Kampinos National Park	N 52°18'15" E 20°26'50" UTM: DC59	Well-heated forest clearings with single elms, maples and oaks.

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Figs 5-6. Locality of *P. ignymontiensis* Lacourt in Kampinos National Park. **5** - the area of the former Bieliny village; **6** - the Norway maple tree where specimens of *P. ignymontiensis* were caught.

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